

Dynamic Goal-Based Adaptive Line of Sight for 3D Path Following: An X300 Case Study

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Abstract—This paper presents a **Dynamic Goal-Based Adaptive Line-of-Sight** algorithm for three-dimensional path-following in autonomous vehicles, addressing limitations in traditional Line-of-Sight methods that use fixed lookahead distances. The proposed approach adjusts the lookahead distance dynamically based on real-time feedback from cross-track errors, vertical-track errors, and path curvature, improving stability and accuracy in complex environments. Five simulation trials using the X300 Autonomous Underwater Vehicle were conducted, varying both lookahead distance (Δ) and velocity (v). Results show that the dynamic method significantly reduces cross-track and vertical-track errors, outperforming fixed lookahead approaches, especially in sharp turns and challenging conditions.

Index Terms—adaptive line-of-sight, dynamic lookahead distance, path-following, 3D navigation, AUV

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Line-of-Sight Guidance and Its Limitations

The Line-of-Sight (LOS) guidance algorithm is widely used for path-following in autonomous vehicles, especially in marine and aerial domains. It calculates a heading angle to minimize cross-track errors (CTE) by guiding the vehicle along a predefined path. Classical LOS, which uses a fixed lookahead distance, performs well in simple environments with smooth trajectories and low speeds [1]–[3]. However, in complex settings with sharp turns or disturbances (e.g., wind and ocean currents), the limitations of a fixed lookahead become apparent. While a longer lookahead distance can reduce oscillations, it may lead to larger tracking errors, while shorter lookahead distances enable quicker corrections but risk instability. This trade-off worsens with increasing speed or complex path curvatures (PC), often leading to higher CTE and vertical-track errors (VTE) in three-dimensional (3D) scenarios [4]. Maintaining stability in 3D path-following is especially challenging with a constant lookahead, requiring both lateral and vertical adjustments [4].

B. Adaptive Line of Sight Methods

To overcome the limitations of fixed lookahead distances, adaptive variations of LOS have been developed. The Adaptive Line-of-Sight (ALOS) method, introduced by Thor I. Fossen et al. [5], [6], dynamically adjusts control parameters in real time to compensate for disturbances such as ocean currents, wind, or waves. This ensures uniform semiglobal exponential

stability (USGES) and enhances the vehicle’s ability to stay on course. However, despite these improvements, many ALOS implementations still use a fixed lookahead distance, leading to increased CTE and VTE, especially in sharp curves or when deviating significantly from the path.

Liu et al. [7] proposed a three-dimensional ALOS (3DOF ALOS) that adjusts the lookahead distance in real time based on factors such as CTE, PC, and speed. By reducing the lookahead in high-curvature sections and increasing it on smoother paths, their method enhances stability and accuracy. Additionally, they extend the lookahead distance as speed increases to prevent destabilizing heading changes, improving performance in 3D environments, such as those faced by autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs). However, their method primarily addresses horizontal-plane errors and overlooks vertical deviations, which are critical for fully 3D path-following. Moreover, it operates independently of Fossen’s ALOS, which effectively manages external disturbances in marine applications. A solution that accounts for both lateral and vertical errors in an integrated manner is still needed.

C. Proposed Dynamic Goal-Based ALOS

We propose a dynamic goal-based ALOS mechanism that builds on Fossen’s framework while addressing its limitations by dynamically adjusting the lookahead distance based on CTE, VTE, and PC in real time. This approach increases the lookahead distance on smoother paths or when errors are minimal, and reduces it during sharp turns or significant deviations. Unlike Liu et al.’s method, which focuses mainly on horizontal-plane deviations, our method includes both lateral and vertical corrections for 3D path-following. Furthermore, it improves on the static lookahead distance used in L. Degorre et al.’s Virtual Reference Point (VRP) method by offering greater flexibility. Integrating real-time adaptability into Fossen’s framework, this method enhances tracking accuracy in complex 3D environments with varying terrain and disturbances, making it ideal for AUVs such as torpedo-shaped models.

II. METHODOLOGY

The dynamic goal-based ALOS method adjusts the lookahead distance Δ using real-time feedback from CTE, VTE, and

PC. Acting as an integral controller, the system accumulates errors (“charging”) and corrects them over time (“discharging”). The update equation is:

$$\Delta(t+1) = \Delta(t) + K_I \sum_{k=0}^t \left(S_0 - \sum_i w_i |e_i(k)| \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, $e_i(k)$ are the error components at time k with weights w_i , and S_0 is the nominal lookahead set-point. K_I is the integral gain influencing the adjustment of Δ .

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

To validate the dynamic ALOS method, five trials were conducted in a ROS2 simulation using the X300 AUV, an under-actuated vehicle with five thrusters. Each trial varied the lookahead distance Δ and velocity v .

The trial configurations were:

- **Trial 1:** Dynamic Δ .
- **Trials 2 and 4:** Fixed $\Delta = 0.5$ with $v = 2.0$ and $v = 0.5$, respectively.
- **Trials 3 and 5:** Fixed $\Delta = 2.0$ with $v = 2.0$ and $v = 0.5$, respectively.

We measured CTE and VTE as the vehicle followed a 3D path, focusing on performance in curves and sharp turns.

Fig. 1. Simulation of the X300 AUV following a 3D path (green line). The black and yellow model shows the vehicle’s pose, and the thick axes represent the goal or Δ frame.

Figure 1 illustrates the X300 AUV navigating a 3D path, adjusting its heading and pitch to minimize CTE and VTE, especially in sharp curves like the dive. The vehicle also faces a water current of 0.2 m/s along the y -axis and 0.1 m/s along the z -axis.

A. Results

Figure 2 compares CTE and VTE across the trials. Trial 1, with dynamic Δ , consistently achieved lower errors, demonstrating better adaptability and stability, especially in sharp turns and complex 3D sections.

Trials 2 and 4, with a short fixed $\Delta = 0.5$, exhibited larger oscillations, particularly in sharp turns. Lower velocity in Trial 4 ($v = 0.5$) resulted in smoother transitions but still significant deviations.

Trials 3 and 5, with a longer fixed $\Delta = 2.0$, reduced oscillations but encountered larger errors during sharp turns, especially at lower velocity (Trial 5, $v = 0.5$).

IV. CONCLUSION

The dynamic ALOS method (Trial 1) minimized both CTE and VTE, outperforming fixed lookahead methods (Trials 2–5) in complex paths. Fixed methods led to either instability at shorter distances or larger errors at longer distances, highlighting the superiority of the dynamic approach in adapting to 3D environments.

Fig. 2. Cross-track and vertical-track errors for different trials with varying lookahead distances and velocities.

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